

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1825	Albrecht Weber	1846	1846	1901		German Indologist and historian	1825-1901
1825	William Balfour Baikie	1854		1864		British Scottish explorer, naturalist and philologist	1825-1864
1825	Friedrich Karl Theodor Zarncke	1854		1891		German philologist	1825-1891
1825	William Ince	1859	1878	1910		British Regius Professor of Divinity at Oxford	1825-1910
1825	Frederick James Furnivall	1861		1910		British English philologist, best known as one of the co-creators of the New English Dictionary	1825-1910
1825	Francis March	1862	No	1911		American polymath, academic, philologist, and lexicographer	1825-2011
1826	Alfred Mézières	1853	1853	1915		French journalist, politician and historian of literature, the oldest member of the French Academy	1826-1915
1827	Wilhelm Bleek	1851	1851	1875		German linguist	1827-1875
1827	William Dwight Whitney	1856	1861	1891		American linguist, philologist, and lexicographer known for his work on Sanskrit grammar and Vedic philology	1827-1894
1827	Joseph Halévy	1872		1907		French Jewish-French Orientalist and traveller	1827-1917
1828	Franjo Rački	1855		1894		Croatian historian, politician and writer	1828-1894
1828	Johan Hendrik van Dale	1863		1872		Dutch teacher, archivist, and lexicographer	1828-1872
1828	Johanna Mestorf	1866		1909	w	German prehistoric archaeologist, the first female museum director in the Kingdom of Prussia and usually said to be the first female professor in Germany	1828-1909
1829	Graziadio Isaia Ascoli	1854		1907		Italian linguist	1829-1907
1829	Konrad Duden	1854		1905		German Gymnasium (high school) teacher who became a philologist	1829-1911
1829	Marcus Jastrow	1855	1855	1893		German-American Talmudic scholar, most famously known for his authorship of the popular and comprehensive A Dictionary of the Targumim, Talmud Babli, Talmud Yerushalmi and Midrashic Literature	1829-1903